

(3,4-dimethoxyarylidine-4-thiazolidinone-2-thione) (0.01 mol) and 6-bromo-4-chloroquinazoline (0.01 mol) was refluxed in pyridine (20 ml) for 4 h. The excess pyridine was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the mixture poured in ice-cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 219° (Found: C, 58.41; H, 3.2; N, 9.02. $C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2S_2$ requires: C, 58.82; H, 3.43; N, 9.29%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1350 (C-N), 1115 (C-S), 675 (C-S), 1600 (C=CH), 1520 (C=N), 1020 (C-O-C of C-OCH₃) and 3300 cm^{-1} (C-H of CH₃); δ 7.5-6.4 (7H, m, ArH and =CH), 7.8 (1H, s, N=CH-N) and 3.9-3.8 (3H, s, 2 × OCH₃ of Ar(OCH₃)₂).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4-5-8,4-SUBSTITUTED-ARYLIDINE-4-THIAZOLIDINONE-2-THIONE-6,8-SUBSTITUTED-QUINAZOLINES (3)

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
X ₁ = X = H					
1.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	210	65
2.	N(OH ₂)	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	205	50
3.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ O ₂	160	50
4.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ O ₂	175	45
X ₁ = Br, X = H					
5.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	218	70
6.	N(OH ₂)	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ O ₂	232	55
7.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	220	50
8.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ BrClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	250	55
X ₁ = I, X = H					
9.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	196	45
10.	N(OH ₂)	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ I ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	240	70
11.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₂ ClIN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	188	70
12.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ O ₂ ClIN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	145	55
X ₁ = X = Br					
13.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	180	50
14.	N(OH ₂)	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	198	52
15.	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	215	55
16.	H	Cl	C ₁₉ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	198	55

Anthelmintic activity: The compound were screened for their cestocidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in rats using the technique of Steward⁸ with slight modifications. The compounds were given orally at doses of 250 mg/kg using 3 rats per experimental group.

Results and Discussion

For anthelmintic activity *in vivo* 12 compounds were tested. The compound having sl. no. 15 (Table 1) showed maximum (65%) activity. The compounds having sl. nos. 3, 5-8, 11 and 14 showed moderate activity (20-50%) and rest of the compounds were inactive.

The data seem to suggest that the introduction of electron-withdrawing groups at R₁ increases the activity whereas that of electron-donating groups at R₁ and R₂ decreases the anthelmintic activity.

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Synthesis of Thiosemicarbazides and Related Compounds as Potential Fungicides

SHISHIR K. SRIVASTAVA, R. B. PATHAK**
and
S. C. BAHTEL*

Department of Chemistry, Gorakhpur University,
Gorakhpur-273 009

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES have N-C=S group, which is an essential structural feature responsible for various biological activities^{1,2}. Various substituted-thiadiazoles³ and triazoles^{4,5} are known to exhibit significant biological activities. Keeping these in view and in continuation of our ongoing research for new antifungal agents^{2,4}, the title compounds have been prepared.

Reaction of α -aryloxypropionyl hydrazines and aryl isothiocyanates yielded 1- α -aryloxypropionyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides (2a-i). Cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides (2a-i) gave 2-arylamino-5- α -aryloxyethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a-i). 3- α -Aryloxyethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (4a-i) were synthesised by refluxing α -aryloxypropionyl hydrazines with aryl isothiocyanates in sodium hydroxide (Scheme 1). Structures of compounds were established by elemental analyses, ir and pmr spectral data.

Fungicidal screening: Twelve compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *A. niger*,

**Department of Chemistry, St. Andrew's College, Gorakhpur.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference. The required hydrazines were prepared by known method.

1- α -(4'-Chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)propionyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2a): A methanolic solution of α -(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)propionyl hydrazine (2.29 g, 0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, (88%), m.p. 150° (Found: N, 11.75; S, 8.72. C₁₇H₁₅ClN₂O₂S requires: N, 11.56; S, 8.80%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 280 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 020 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.4-1.5 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.7-3.9 (3H, b, NH), 4.7-4.9 (1H, q, CH) and 6.9-7.6 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (2b-i) were prepared (Table 1).

2-Anilino-5- α -(4'-chloro-3'-methylphenoxy)ethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3a): Thiosemicarbazide (2a; 1.82 g, 0.005 mol) was dissolved in cold and minimum amount of concentrated sulphuric acid. The solution was kept at room temperature for 2 h, stirred occasionally and then poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, (94.7%), m.p. 189° (Found: N, 11.94; S, 9.47. C₁₇H₁₄ClN₃OS

- a; R=4-Cl, 3-OH, R'=H,
- b; R=4-Cl, 3-OH, R'=4-Cl
- c; R=4-Cl, 3-OH, R'=4-OCH₃,
- d; R=2,4-(OH)₂, R'=H
- e; R=2,4-(OH)₂, R'=4-Cl
- f; R=2,4-(OH)₂, R'=4-OCH₃,
- g; R=4-(OH)₂O, R'=H
- h; R=4-(OH)₂O, R'=4-Cl
- i; R=4-(OH)₂O, R'=4-OCH₃,

Scheme 1

H. oryzae and *C. sacchari* using agar-plate technique* and found to be moderately active. In general, the presence of chlorine and/or methoxy group invariably increased the antifungal activity of the compounds. The triazoles were more active than the corresponding thiadiazoles which were relatively more antifungal than the corresponding thiosemicarbazides.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	4-Cl, 3-OH	H	88.0	150	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
2b	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-Cl	92.5	124	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
2c	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-OCH ₃	70.0	121	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
2d	2,4-(OH) ₂	H	94.0	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S
2e	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-Cl	89.0	143	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
2f	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-OCH ₃	88.8	120	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
2g	4-(OH) ₂ O	H	91.7	54	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S
2h	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-Cl	94.7	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S
2i	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-OCH ₃	94.8	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S
3a	4-Cl, 3-OH	H	94.7	189	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS
3b	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-Cl	79.0	178	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS
3c	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-OCH ₃	94.7	162	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
3d	2,4-(OH) ₂	H	57.9	117	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS
3e	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-Cl	65.4	201	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS
3f	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-OCH ₃	53.6	150	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ S
3g	4-(OH) ₂ O	H	90.0	172	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS
3h	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-Cl	90.0	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS
3i	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-OCH ₃	52.6	200	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ S
4a	4-Cl, 3-OH	H	71.4	195	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ OS
4b	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-Cl	76.8	211	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS
4c	4-Cl, 3-OH	4-OCH ₃	78.6	176	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S
4d	2,4-(OH) ₂	H	87.1	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS
4e	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-Cl	87.6	98	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS
4f	2,4-(OH) ₂	4-OCH ₃	82.3	172	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ S
4g	4-(OH) ₂ O	H	79.4	166	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OS
4h	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-Cl	79.7	203	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS
4i	4-(OH) ₂ O	4-OCH ₃	83.7	160	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ S

* All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

requires: N, 12.16; S, 9.26%; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200 (NH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 030 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 650 cm^{-1} (C-S-C); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.6-1.7 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.4 (1H, s, NH), 5.5-5.7 (1H, q, CH) and 6.8-7.6 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (3b-1) were prepared (Table 1).

3- α -(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy)ethyl-4-p-methoxyphenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (4f): A mixture of α -(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)propionyl hydrazine (2.08 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (1.65 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in sodium hydroxide solution (8%; 20 ml) for 5 h, then cooled, poured into large excess of water, stirred and filtered. The filtrate on acidification yielded a solid which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, (82.3%), m.p. 172° (Found: N, 11.92; S, 8.87. C₁₈H₂₁N₃O₂S requires: N, 11.83; S, 9.01%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 120 (NH), 2 700 (SH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 010 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and $1 070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.4-1.5 (3H, d, CH₃), 1.9 (3H, s, *p*-CH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, *o*-CH₃), 3.2 (1H, s, SH), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.0-5.2 (1H, q, CH) and 6.3-7.1 (7H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (4a-e, g-1) were prepared (Table 1).

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Synthesis of some New Phenothiazine Derivatives

M. B. HOGALE* and DILIP S. DESHMUKH

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

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PHENOTHIAZINE and its derivatives possess various biological activities¹. As a part of our research programme, we report the synthesis of some new *N*-substituted tricyclic hydrazides, thiosemicarbazides and five-membered heterocycles.

The key intermediates, *N*-substituted phenothiazine thiosemicarbazides were prepared by the reaction of appropriate ethyl/chloroformate, ethyl chloroacetate, ethyl bromopropionate and diethyl bromomalonate with phenothiazine in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ followed by the reaction with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol to form the corresponding hydrazides (2a-d). These hydrazides (2) on refluxing with phenyl isothiocyanate in alcohol gave the corresponding *N*₁₀-substituted phenothiazine thiosemicarbazides (3a-d), which were further cyclised to the five-membered heterocyclic *N*₁₀-substituted phenothiazines (4-6; Scheme 1).

